

Risk factors for electrical and mechanical complications after st-elevation myocardial infarction

Factores de riesgo de complicaciones eléctricas y mecánicas tras infarto agudo de miocardio con elevación ST

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Abstract

Despite the overall improvement in ST-elevation myocardial infarction (STEMI) management and the significant decrease in cases within the past decade, it remains one of the leading causes of death worldwide. It is well known that STEMI carries an important risk of developing electrical complications (EC) and mechanical complications (MC), which account for most of the in-hospital mortality in these groups. Although revascularization therapy, either percutaneous coronary intervention (PCI) or fibrinolysis, has significantly decreased the incidence of EC and MC, they are still a major health concern. Therefore, the initial management of STEMI is vital but is not limited only to PCI or thrombolysis; it also involves the management of possible complications. Predicting the likelihood of these complications is highly useful for physicians so that preventive measures can be taken. This review aims to identify risk factors in STEMI patients associated with the onset of EC and MC. Developing predictive models for EC and MC is a pending task, but that would significantly benefit both the patients and the medical community.

Keywords: ST-elevation myocardial infarction, cardiovascular mortality, coronary artery disease, electrical complications, mechanical complications.

Resumen

A pesar de la mejoría global en el manejo del infarto agudo de miocardio con elevación del ST (IAMCEST) y de la marcada disminución de casos en la última década, sigue siendo una de las principales causas de muerte a nivel mundial. Es bien sabido que el IAMCEST conlleva un importante riesgo de desarrollar complicaciones eléctricas (CE) y complicaciones mecánicas (CM), las cuales representan la mayor parte de la mortalidad intrahospitalaria en estos pacientes. Aunque la terapia de reperfusión, ya sea mediante intervención coronaria percutánea (ICP) o fibrinólisis, ha reducido de forma significativa la incidencia de CE y CM, estas siguen siendo un problema sanitario de gran relevancia. Por ello, el manejo inicial del IAMCEST es vital, pero no se limita únicamente a la ICP o a la trombólisis; también incluye el abordaje de las posibles complicaciones. Predecir la probabilidad de dichas complicaciones es de gran utilidad para el médico, ya que permite instaurar medidas preventivas. Esta revisión tiene como objetivo identificar los factores de riesgo en pacientes con IAMCEST asociados con la aparición de CE y CM. El desarrollo de modelos predictivos para CE y CM es una tarea aún pendiente, pero que podría aportar un beneficio significativo tanto para los pacientes como para la comunidad médica.

Palabras clave: infarto agudo de miocardio con elevación del ST, mortalidad cardiovascular, enfermedad coronaria, complicaciones eléctricas, complicaciones mecánicas.

Ischemic heart disease (IHD) ranks as the most prevalent form of cardiovascular disease (CVD); affecting 1,655 out of every 100,000 individuals, or approximately 1.7% of the world's population. Likewise, every year, over nine million deaths are attributable to IHD globally, making it the number one cause of death, disability, and decreased life expectancy worldwide¹. Although age-adjusted incidence rates show a promising decrease, the overall number of cases is growing, probably due to extended population aging and the presence of comorbidities such as obesity, hypertension (HT), and diabetes mellitus (DM)². Moreover, management of IHD, hospitalizations, treatments, revascularization procedures and many other factors generate a significant financial impact. By 2030, IHD alone will generate over US\$1 trillion in healthcare costs³.

ST-segment elevation myocardial infarction (STEMI), despite not being the most prevalent variant of IHD, is the most severe form of presentation. STEMI has the highest rates of mortality, disability, and post-infarction complications out of all the forms of IHD⁴. While some studies reported high in-hospital mortality for STEMI⁵, with the advent of new strategies and protocols, other authors have reported decreasing rates of in-hospital and post-discharge mortality⁶. However, STEMI patients, even those treated with percutaneous coronary intervention (PCI), have a significant risk of developing infarction-associated complications. It is well known that STEMI carries out an important risk of developing electrical complications (EC) and mechanical complications (MC), which account for most of the in-hospital mortality in these groups⁷. In fact, cardiogenic shock (CS), which can happen as a result of any EC or MC, is the leading cause of in-hospital mortality in STEMI patients⁸.

On the other hand, EC, namely arrhythmias, have been observed to appear in up to 90% of STEMI patients, out of which 64.5% tend to be lethal; including ventricular tachycardia (VT), complete auriculoventricular block (CAVB), ventricular fibrillation (VF), and atrial fibrillation (AF). Mortality rates of patients with lethal arrhythmias against those who develop non-lethal arrhythmias is considerably distant⁹. Therefore, the initial management of STEMI is vital but is not limited only to PCI or thrombolysis; it also involves the management of possible complications. Predicting the likelihood of these complications is highly useful for physicians so that preventive

measures can be taken¹⁰. This review aims to identify risk factors in STEMI patients associated with the onset of EC and MC.

RISK FACTORS FOR MECHANICAL COMPLICATIONS AFTER ST-ELEVATION MYOCARDIAL INFARCTION

The most commonly encountered MC after STEMI are acute mitral regurgitation (AMR), secondary to papillary muscle rupture, ventricular septal defect (VSD), ventricular pseudoaneurysm (VPA) or aneurysm (VA), and free wall rupture (FWR)¹¹. The incidence of MC remains low compared to EC, but the associated mortality rate is remarkably high, especially in older patients¹². Most of these complications need timely recognition and management for optimal resolution; however, differentiation between mechanical STEMI complications from noncardiac shock causes often requires invasive hemodynamic assessments and noninvasive imaging, significantly delaying the diagnosis and worsening the prognosis. For that reason, establishing proper alert protocols based on risk factors can improve the delay in diagnosis¹³.

Despite improvements in revascularization strategies and protocol care of STEMI, the incidence of MC has remained unmodified. The lack of changes in the incidence of MC despite proper management could be explained by the increasing prevalence of cardiovascular risk factors like HT, DM, and aging^{7,14}. Overall, MC seem to share common risk factors while keeping independent ones. For example, patients with any MC tend to be older, female, with a history of heart failure (HF), chronic kidney disease (CKD), and often present the MC on their first STEMI^{15,16}. Additionally, socioeconomic status differences showed a significant role in the health outcomes after STEMI; namely, the highest socioeconomic class were more prompt to consult earlier and to be treated in specialized cardiac facilities compared to lower socioeconomic classes¹⁷.

An observational study assessed the epidemiological aspects of AMR following 1000 STEMI patients treated with PCI. According to the study the overall prevalence of AMR was 29.4% for a total of 294 patients, graded as mild (n=224 [76%]), moderate (n=61 [21%]), and severe (n=9 [3%]). Regarding risk factors, it was reported that patients with AMR tend to be older, with worse left ventricular ejection fraction (LVEF) and creatinine clearance; moreover, AMR patients had higher rates of HTA, HF, previous STEMI, and severe flow-limitation in the circumflex and right coronary artery. Furthermore, revascularization after 72 hours from symptom onset was significantly associated with AMR incidence¹⁸. Nogi et al.¹⁹ performed a similar study but only considered patients with severe AMR. The prevalence of severe AMR was 4.7%, similar but discretely higher than the above study. According to the results, older patients and females had

a significantly higher risk of developing severe AMR; likewise, the AMR group had a larger left atrial diameter and left ventricular end-systolic volume.

On the other hand, the incidence of VSD after STEMI is under 0.5%, making it a markedly rare condition, with a mortality rate as high as 80% when left untreated²⁰. Due to the scarcity of VSD cases, epidemiological data is either old or somewhat unspecific. As stated with other MC, older age and delayed reperfusion therapy increase the risk of VSD²¹. A more recent review, concerning VSD specifically, reported that patients over 65 years, males, and white had the highest risk according to demographic factors. On the other hand, patients with inferior and anterior myocardial infarction were more commonly implicated with the development of VSD, in contrast to lateral and posterior myocardial infarction²². Similarly, another study found that a high Killip classification and high lactate levels were also associated with VSD and other MC¹².

Consequently, FWR is the most commonly reported MC after STEMI; however, since most cases present as out-of-hospital sudden cardiac deaths (SCD) and autopsies are not routinely performed, accurate incidence numbers are unknown²³. Moreno et al.²⁴ studied 1,375 STEMI patients treated either with PCI or thrombolysis. It was reported after univariate analysis that patients over 70 years and females had a significantly greater risk of FWR. Likewise, anterior infarction location and treatment delay greater than 2 hours after consultation were independent risk factors for FWR. Lastly, it was reported that the risk of FWR was significantly greater in patients treated with thrombolysis than those treated with PCI²⁴. On the other hand, Yoneyama et al.²⁵ reported that delayed patient consultation for STEMI was significantly associated with FWR incidence and mortality. After adjustments for age, sex, Killip class, CKD, and LVEF, the hazard ratio (HR) for a delay in consultation was of over 48 hours was 2.25 (95% CI; 1.22-4.15).

Lastly, VA and VPA are complications that can develop from other conditions such as cardiovascular surgery, chest trauma, or infective endocarditis, but they are most commonly associated with STEMI²⁶. Zhang et al.²⁷ performed a study to determine potential predictors for VA after STEMI. The investigation involved 1823 STEMI patients, out of which 103 had a VA and were compared to 206 patients without VA. Analyses showed that those with regional wall motion abnormality (RWMA) in the left ventricular wall had the highest risk of developing a VA (OR 13.17, 95% CI; 2.21-78.57, $p=0.005$), followed by RWMA in the apex (OR 7.93, 95% CI; 2.22-28.30, $p=0.001$). Other factors such as female sex, elevated N-terminal pro-brain natriuretic peptide, PCI delay, and QS-waves on initial electrocardiogram were independently associated with VA formation but not as strongly as the aforementioned factors.

RISK FACTORS FOR ELECTRICAL COMPLICATIONS AFTER ST-ELEVATION MYOCARDIAL INFARCTION

Regarding EC, many variables need to be considered to elaborate proper affirmations, like the type of arrhythmia, and the wall affected by the infarction. Firstly, the incidence of post-STEMI arrhythmias can be as high as 90% of the total population, meaning that most population is at risk, making it difficult to define specific risk factors. However, it has been reported that male patients tend to have a higher risk of developing any arrhythmia⁹. Another study assessed specifically the epidemiological characteristics of patients that developed VF. It was found that STEMI cases had higher rates of VF than non-STEMI (OR 2.29, 95% CI; 1.75-2.99). Likewise, female sex, HT, and prior myocardial infarctions acted as protective factors. However, the protective aspect of HT was hypothesized to result from proper antihypertensive treatment²⁸.

The GEVAMI study compared patients with and without VF on their first STEMI and identified independent risk factors prior to STEMI. For instance, people aged below 60 with a family history of SCD, absence of previous angina episodes, history of AF, and high alcohol intake were significantly associated with the appearance of VF after the first STEMI²⁹. Concerning STEMI-related properties, it has been reported that infarct size and location can significantly alter the incidence of VF³⁰. In that matter, patients presenting with high ST elevation scores, short RR intervals, or prolonged PR and QRS intervals carry a higher risk of VF^{31,32}. The compromised artery also influences the incidence of ventricular arrhythmias. According to a Belgian case-control study, patients with occlusion of the left coronary artery had a higher risk of developing VF than those with an occluded right coronary artery³³.

On the other hand, new-onset AF (NOAF) is a reasonably frequent post-STEMI arrhythmia and correlates with subsequent cardiovascular mortality. A systematic review of eleven studies containing over 9500 patients reported that older patients and increased heart rate parameters on admission showed a significant positive association with NOAF³⁴. According to Carnicelli et al.³⁵, patients that develop NOAF after STEMI tend to be older and have more comorbidities than those without NOAF; namely, HT, DM, obesity, hypercholesterolemia, and CKD showed the most relevance.

Similarly, Iqbal et al.³⁶ reported that NOAF was more prevalent in males, although the difference was not statistically significant. Moreover, DM, current smoking, and HT showed a significant positive correlation with NOAF. Notably, HT had the strongest association among all the comorbidities for NOAF. Moreover, other authors investigated the relevance of atrial cardiomyopathy (ACM) markers as predictors of NOAF in STEMI patients. Patients were segmented in tertiles according to their P-wave terminal force in ECG lead V1, left atrial dimension,

and B-type natriuretic peptide levels. The results showed the higher the patients ranked in these groups, the higher the risk of developing NOAF³⁷. Furthermore, the uric acid/albumin ratio (UAR) impact on NOAF incidence has also been studied. According to Selçuk et al.³⁸, patients with NOAF had higher UAR than those without NOAF. Multivariate logistic regression models confirmed that UAR was an independent predictor for NOAF in STEMI patients (OR: 6.951, 95% CI; 2.978-16.28, $p < 0.001$).

Conclusions

Despite the overall improvement in STEMI management and the significant decrement in cases within the past decade, STEMI remains one of the leading causes of death worldwide. STEMI-associated complications are relatively frequent, and many have high mortality rates; therefore, the management of these patients is far from over after revascularization. Although revascularization therapy, either PCI or fibrinolysis, has significantly decreased the incidence of EC and MC, they are still a major health concern. These complications share a fair amount of risk factors, but they also have independent risk factors that must be considered. Individualizing each case according to its risk factors is critical to improve complications management and prevention. Developing predictive models for EC and MC is a pending task, but that would significantly benefit both the patients and the medical community.

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